

EXPERIMENTS AND NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS OF SMC IN COMPRESSION MOLDING

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ABSTRACT

Experimental investigation and numerical simulation were performed to study the compression molding of SMC. Laboratory scaled molds were designed and built for experimental study of the SMC charges with different colored layers to visualize the flow patterns. Temperature and flow patterns inside SMC charge were measured with various process parameters such as mold temperature, mold geometry and closing speed. A thermo-viscoplastic finite element program was developed to simulate compression molding. In the analytical study, deformation of the material was modeled by using the flow rule into which fiber distribution is taken account. A kinetic model was adopted to describe the cure behavior. The results of analysis and experiments were compared and showed good agreements. The experimental findings combined with analytical results provided a sound understanding of SMC in compression molding.

Keywords: SMC(Sheet Molding Compound), Compression Molding, Process Simulation, Thermo-viscoplastic Finite Element Method, Fiber Distributions, Curing Kinetic Model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sheet Molding Compound(SMC) has wide applications with its relatively low cost, light weight and design possibility. Compression molding is commonly employed in the processing of SMC to manufacture certain desired parts. Typical SMC products are thin plate with ribs as substructures on a side, which reduce the weight of structures without losing the stiffness. During the molding process, serious problems occur around the intersections of the main part and substructures.

To characterize the flow properties of SMC under compression molding, a squeeze flow rheometer has been widely used.[1] The SMC flow as a combination of an in-plane extensional resistance due to fiber-resin interaction and a friction response at the mold interface[2] has been modeled. Mold filling of SMC has been studied experimentally.[3,4] They pointed out that the nonuniform flow resulted in a differential shrinkage during molding, a non-uniform pressure pattern, and frozen residual stresses in the cured part, which would affect the fiber orientation and consequently the final mechanical properties and cosmetic appearance. Useful results have been obtained by the generalized Hele-Shaw's flow model(GHS).[5] A series of kinetic models for unsaturated polyester resins based on the usually accepted reaction mechanism of free radical copolymerizations were developed.[6,7] These mechanistic models not only provided the necessary kinetic information for the heat transfer modelling, but also elucidated the functions of initiators, inhibitors and monomers in the reaction up to the medium conversion region.

The purpose of the study is to investigate the effects of process parameters to the flow and the curing of SMC during compression molding. Experiments with T-shaped molds were performed to characterize the process parameters. For flow study, the flow pattern was visualized with charges of different colored layers. A numerical simulation program by the rigid-thermoviscoplastic finite element method has been developed for the analytical study of the flow and the curing of SMC. The fiber contents distribution during molding was modeled and incorporated into the program. By establishing the simulation tool, it is expected to help the process design of compression molding.

2. METHOD OF ANALYSIS

2.1 Flow and Heat Transfer Model

The problems are limited to quasi-static and infinitesimal deformation based on the rigid-viscoplastic approach in the formulation.[8] The flow-rule (or the constitutive equations) describes the relationship between the stresses and the strain-rates in the plastically deforming body as follows:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{\dot{\bar{\epsilon}}}{\bar{\sigma}} \sigma'_{ij} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\bar{\epsilon}} = (\frac{2}{3} \dot{\epsilon}'_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}'_{ij})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ represents the effective or the equivalent strain-rate in terms of the plastic components of the strain-rate tensor, $\dot{\epsilon}'_{ij}$, and $\bar{\sigma} = (\frac{3}{2} \sigma'_{ij} \sigma'_{ij})^{\frac{1}{2}}$, the effective or the equivalent stress in terms of the components of deviatoric stress tensor, σ'_{ij} .

The energy balance equation for heat transfer analysis is expressed as

$$(k_i T_{,i})_{,i} - \rho C_p \dot{T} + \dot{r} = 0 \quad , \quad (2)$$

where T is temperature, \dot{T} , temperature rate, k_i , the thermal conductivity in the i -th direction, ρ , the density, C_p , the specific heat at constant pressure, and \dot{r} , the rate of heat generation per unit volume. The rate of heat generation is due to the plastic work and the chemical reaction.

The model proposed by Stevenson[6] and Lee[7] was adopted for the cure study, which was derived by considering the function of every major component in the SMC compound and assuming that the SMC reaction can be described as a combination of three steps: initiation, inhibition, and propagation. Reaction starts only after the number of initiator radicals created is equal to the effective number of inhibitor molecules initially presented. The induction time is determined by

$$2f(I_o - I) = 2fI_o(1 - e^{-\int_0^t k_d dt}) \geq qZ_o \quad . \quad (3)$$

The reaction propagates and generates heat when $t > t_z$,

$$\dot{r} = H_R M_o \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = H_R M_o \{ 2fI_r k_p (1 - \alpha) (1 - e^{-\int_0^{t-t_z} k_d d(t-t_z)}) \} \quad . \quad (4)$$

The heat generated during the chemical reaction is added into the energy balance equation during the heat transfer analysis. In the above equations, k_d is an initiator decomposition rate constant, I , the concentration of the initiator, f , the initiator efficiency, Z_o , the initial concentration of inhibitor, q , the inhibitor efficiency, k_p , the propagation rate constant, H_R , heat of reaction, and M_o , the initial concentration of monomer. The kinetic parameters, k_d and k_p are assumed to be Arrhenius temperature-dependent throughout the entire cure, where

$$k_d = A_d \exp(-E_d / RT) \quad \text{and} \quad k_p = A_p \exp(-E_p / RT) \quad . \quad (5)$$

2.2 Fiber Content Distribution

During the molding process, the fiber contents in SMC charge distribute and affect to the material properties and to the quality of final product. To predict the so-called "resin-rich" and "fiber-rich" regions, a model for fiber movement is needed.[9] The motion of a single fiber during compression molding SMC, depends on the shape of fiber, the mutual restraint forces due to the frictional and the interwound forces of fibers, and the molding process variables. If we assume that the state of the flow is steady and the gravity and the buoyancy are neglected, the fiber velocity becomes,[10]

$$v_f = v_c - \Delta v = v_c - \frac{K}{\mu_{eq}} v_c^n \quad , \quad (6)$$

where μ is the viscosity and the subscript 'f' denotes the fiber, 'c', the average of composite material and 'eq' denotes the equivalent value. The normal component of the relative velocities of the composite and the fiber along a straight line is

$$\Delta v_n = \frac{K}{\mu_{eq}} (v_c)_n^n \quad (7)$$

If we denote V_f and Q as the fiber volume and the volume fraction of fiber in the composite, respectively, the volume of the fiber across the straight line of length l , is determined as,

$$\Delta V_f = \int_l (\Delta v_n) Q dl (\Delta t) \quad (8)$$

Figure 1. Changes of fiber volume in a rectangular element.

In a subdomain of the composite (Figure 1), the volume changes of fibers during a time step, Δt , in each subregion can be determined as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(V_f)_{31} &= \int_{l_{13}} (\Delta v_n) Q dl (\Delta t), \text{ and} \\ \Delta(V_f)_{42} &= \int_{l_{24}} (\Delta v_n) Q dl (\Delta t). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The volume fraction of fiber at a point after time Δt becomes,

$$Q^{t+\Delta t} = \frac{Q' V'_c + \sum \Delta V'_f}{V'_c} = Q' + \frac{\sum \Delta V'_f}{V'_c} \quad (10)$$

Figure 2. Initial workpiece on the lower mold and thermocouple positions.

3. CONDITIONS OF EXPERIMENT AND SIMULATION

3.1 Equipment Set-up

In order to investigate the flow and cure mechanisms during compression process, laboratory scaled molds were designed and built. Parameters such as mold temperature, closing speed and rib geometry were changed to characterize their effects on the process.

Electrically controlled heat elements inside upper and lower molds retained the desired mold temperature precisely. Two different ram speeds were chosen for the closing speed effect on the molding. In order to obtain the intermediate state of material flow, compression was stopped and maintained a constant height during the process. Two identical lower molds except the rib depth were prepared for the effect of rib geometry. Data acquisition system was employed to record temperature histories measured from the workpiece and the mold during the process. Two K type

thermocouples were embedded in the workpiece and three thermocouples in the molds.

The initial charge for 9.5 mm rib had dimension of 100(W) x 48 (L) x 9.2 (H) mm and length was increased to 52 mm for 14.25 mm rib to make equivalent plane thickness. Four layers with two different colors were alternately stacked for the visual flow patterns. As shown in Figure 2, initial charge was placed such that the material flow could be blocked in width direction to satisfy a plane-strain condition.

3.2 Simulation Conditions

The flow stress of SMC can be determined with simple compression tests. Cylindrical specimens with diameter 44.0mm and the height 9.0mm were compressed in the UTM with constant ram speeds of 0.2mm/sec, 2.0mm/sec, and 4.0mm/sec at constant temperatures of 20°C, 35°C, 50°C, and 65°C. The temperature-dependent coefficients $\eta_o(T)$ and $m(T)$ in the flow stress of SMC expressed as,

$$\bar{\sigma} = \eta_o(T) \dot{\epsilon}^{m(T)} \quad (11)$$

The coefficients obtained from the compression test are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_o(T) &= 8.213 \times 10^{-4} \exp(2182.325 / T) \quad (\text{kgf} / \text{mm}^2), \text{ and} \\ m(T) &= 1.450 - 2.5145 \times 10^{-9} \exp(5775.838 / T) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Figure 3. Initial meshes for simulation of T-shape compression molding.

The thermal and kinetic properties of SMC compound used in this study are summarized in Table 1. The same molding conditions as experiments were applied to the simulations. In order to see the effects of process parameters on the temperature histories, two different molding conditions for each three parameters, or the mold temperature, the rib geometry and the closing speed, were applied. The processing parameters used in the computation are as follows:

- Mold temperature: 130°C and 150°C,
- Closing speed: 0.5 and 2.0mm/sec,
- Dwelling time: 10.0 seconds,
- The friction factor: 0.5.

The initial mesh for simulation of T-shape molding is shown in Figure 3. The meshes of workpiece have been remeshed whenever the elements were distorted severely. Remeshings were done about 9 to 11 times for each flow simulation and the number of nodes in the workpiece was 200 to 700 after remeshings.

Table 1. Thermal and kinetic properties of SMC charge.

$\rho C_p (N / \text{mm}^2 - K)$	2.04	$A_d (\text{appr. unit})$	7.82×10^{13}
$k (N / \text{sec} - K)$	1.985	$E_d / R(K)$	15454
$h_{\text{lub}} (N / \text{mm} - \text{sec} - K)$	0.498	$A_p (\text{appr. unit})$	1.71×10^{13}
$h_{\text{env}} (N / \text{mm} - \text{sec} - K)$	0.00498	$E_p / R(K)$	8410
$H_R M_o (N - \text{mm} / \text{mm}^3)$	140.0	$2fI_o (\text{mole} / \text{g} - \text{SMC})$	7.32×10^{-5}
		$qZ_o (\text{mole} / \text{g} - \text{SMC})$	7.32×10^{-7}

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Flow Pattern

The measured and computed flows along the planar and the rib directions with two different rib depths are shown in Figure 4. The flow front propagation ratios in the figure are defined as the charge length divided by mold length for the planar flow and the flowed depth of charge divided by the rib depth for the rib flow, respectively. Since the measured lengths have distributions for a

specimen, the maximum and minimum ranges are shown with the error bars in Figure 4.

Planar flows in both cases show similar trends. It is observed, however, that the amount of flow into the rib is affected by rib depth. For the 9.5 mm rib, material filling in the rib is completed with planar filling. But material filling in 14.25 mm rib is found to be slow until planar filling is completed. Computational result shows the same trend for flow front propagation. Although the data are not shown in this paper, slower closing speed is better in terms of fillings in both planar and rib directions with 14.25 mm rib. With 9.5 mm rib, however, closing speed did not affect material fillings. From the moment of compression started, it takes less than 10 seconds to finish material flow. Therefore, mold temperature is thought not to affect the flow front speed and corresponding results were obtained from the experiments and computations.

Figure 4. Flow front propagation ratios with closing speed 2.0 mm/s, mold temperature 130°C.

Figure 5. Flow Patterns at the cross section of SMC charge

The cross section of specimen was cut and photographed. By following the boundaries of layers, each photograph was reproduced by hand drawing for a clear view. In Figure 5, the experimental and the simulated flow lines are displayed and the followings are observed:

- 1st and 4th layers were gathered at the side area and inside the rib, which coincide with the results by other researchers.[2,3]
- Most of 2nd and 3rd layers, enclosed by 1st and 4th layers, did not reach the side of mold.
- With faster closing speed and deeper rib, the flows of 2nd and 3rd layers into the rib increased.

The flow patterns obtained from the simulation show insufficient amounts of outer layers(1st and 4th layers) enclosing inner layers, compared to those of experiments. It can be explained with the use of overestimated strain-rate sensitivity in the flow resistance. Even though the flow stress or the viscosity of SMC is lowered at the hotter region near the mold surface, the highly developed strain-rate, in turn, increases the flow stress or the flow resistance, which prohibits the flow.

4.2 Temperature and Cure

Temperature histories were measured at two different locations in SMC workpiece during the molding and the curing process. Initial locations of the thermocouples in the workpiece are shown in Figure 2. Since the thermocouples moved into the rib as the material flows, temperatures were recorded at the positions different with the initial ones. By comparison of temperature profile (a) and (b) in Figure 6, the effect of mold temperature on SMC cure process is clearly shown. In the figure, both the cure time and peak temperature agree with the experiments well. At the higher mold temperature, cure takes place much faster than at the lower temperature. Because 10 seconds were given as the dwelling time, temperatures obtained from thermocouples near the lower mold surface is higher at the beginnings.

(a) Mold Temp.:150°C, Rib:9.5mm, Speed:0.5mm/s

(b) Mold Temp.:130°C, Rib:9.5mm, Speed:0.5mm/s

(c) Mold Temp.:130°C, Rib:9.5mm, Speed:2.0mm/s

(d) Mold Temp.:130°C, Rib:14.25mm, Speed:2.0mm/s

Figure 6. Temperature variations with different molding conditions.

The peak times in the 14.15 mm rib occurred later than the ones in 9.5 mm rib in general. Consequently, the longer time was needed to complete cure for the workpiece with deeper rib. There is no apparent effect of closing speed shown on the temperature history. The distributions of temperature after mold filling and at 80 sec after the process begins are shown in Figure 7. In the earlier time, the righthand part of SMC charge becomes hottest because of the largest surface area

for heat transfer. Since the rib is completely filled after the mold filling in the horizontal part, the temperature at the bottom is lower than that of the righthand part. In the figures, the cure patterns in the workpiece can be estimated.

In general, the reaction starts after an induction time and passes through a maximum rate, then drops down to zero rate. Figure 8 shows the distributions of fractional conversion at 80sec. Figure 9 shows the induction time contour from the cure simulation including mold filling. The area with the shortest induction time (i.e., earliest reaction) are at the right-hand part and the bottom corners of the rib because of the largest surface area for heat transfer. The area with the longest induction time appears in the middle region of the rib. This is because of the long distance for heat conduction and the material flow to fill the rib before heat can be conducted into that area from the mold surface. It should be noted that the heat transfer from the bottom mold to the charge during the dwelling would generate an asymmetric cure pattern through the part. In other words, the material near the bottom surface tends to react earlier than that at other locations. The curing process can be summarized that the material in the center of the rib substructure cures slower than that in the flat plate part.

4.3 Fiber Distribution

Figure 10 shows the distributions of the fiber contents in terms of the volume fraction after mold filling. It is easily seen that the fibers are dense near the top surface and around the rib corners, which is known as 'fiber-rich' area. On the other hand, the resin-rich area appeared just below the top surface in the center, which is frequently observed but not measured quantitatively in experiments. With the slower closing speed, the formation of the resin-rich area covered with dense 'fiber-bridge' at the top surface is clear, which may cause the sink mark during cooling because of the material inhomogeneity, while the fiber distribution is more uniform with the faster closing speed.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Effects of various process parameters on the SMC compression molding, such as the mold temperature, the closing speed, and the rib geometry, were characterized by experiments and numerical study. Proposed numerical model predicted the curing and the fiber distributions of SMC, which are related to the formations of defects. The computer program developed in this study can be a useful process designing tool for SMC product.

Acknowledgements : The authors wish to thank Mr. Young-Min Choi of Hong-Ik University for his assistant in the computational works.

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